

Local Government in Spain

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Spain is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

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People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Spain: An Introduction

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The 1978 Spanish Constitution created a legal context that favors citizen participation. Under Article 9(2), all public authorities (and thus local governments) should 'facilitate the participation of all citizens in political, economic, cultural and social life' and Article 23(1) provides, as a fundamental right, (i.e., enforceable before a court of law, including the Spanish Constitutional Court) that citizens are entitled to 'participate in public affairs, directly or through representatives'. In compliance with the constitutional provisions, the Spanish Local Government Act (Act 7/1985, of April 2, LBRL) lays down a set of guarantees and procedures ensuring public participation at a local level and currently displays three sets of legal provisions regarding citizen participation. First, the so-called 'open council' or 'town meeting' (*concejo abierto*), a form of local government for small municipalities (usually not exceeding 100 people) where citizens gather in an assembly to rule the town (Article 29 LBRL). Second, Article 18(1)(b) LBRL expressly grants the enforceable right 'to participate' to all residents. Third, this same act also provides for several mandates addressed to local governments with the aim of promoting citizen participation (Articles 69 to 72 LBRL).

In sum, national and regional provisions have created a legal framework favoring citizen participation. However, these legal provisions often fail to implement tools and mechanisms to make such public participation effective. For a country like Spain where levels of social capital and citizens' involvement in public affairs are rather low, it is up to each municipality to implement strategies that make peoples participation effective. Actually, there are major differences between municipalities that simply allow for participation, yet they do not facilitate it or purposefully promote it and others that facilitate it and promote an inclusive participation. Differences can be explained by factors such as the availability of resources in place, a municipality's social fabric or the political orientation of the municipal government.

Recently, the presence of new political parties in municipal councils during the 2015-2019 period (classified as 'alternative left', such as Podemos), has reinvigorated participation in those municipalities ruled by them (including major Spanish cities like Madrid, Barcelona, Valencia or Zaragoza) emphasizing the importance of open and inclusive decision-making mechanisms and putting them in place.

These local strategies can take several forms but they respond to one of the two main types of participatory logic: people's participation is either implemented through permanent institutions or through processes open to all citizens. In both cases, the impact and results of citizens' participation (i.e. level of citizen information on the projects, transparency in policy making, political accountability) is an open question to be analyzed.

As the most relevant example of the first strategy, we find the so-called advisory boards or advisory councils (*consejos consultivos*). They can be either sectoral (engaging public and private actors in connection with a sector or sector-specific policies: the elderly, culture, sports or education, among others) or territorial (the actors engaged and the interests at stake revolve around a given district or neighborhood). These advisory boards are the oldest and most commonly used participation mechanisms in local governments in Spain. Despite their little media visibility (they are somewhat overshadowed by the new forms of online citizen participation, popular consultations or participatory budgeting), they are probably the main form of dialogue between governments and organized groups. Some of the municipal councils that took office in 2015 are drawing up plans to reinvigorate and activate advisory boards. Madrid, for instance, is turning them into bodies more open to citizens and not only to the associations' representatives.

In the second type, we find strategies like local referendums and public consultation processes in local planning. Concerning referendums, they are hardly held in Spain due to its regulation, that requires the national government's prior authorization, thereby subjecting this participation initiative to stringent procedural requirements unparalleled in other legal systems. But public consultations have experienced a remarkable increase recently. They have typically played a prominent role regarding two areas: urban planning and local budgeting, but there are also other fields where these consultations are carried out, including participatory budgeting.

In addition to this, recent legal provisions (local, regional and national) have regulated bottom-up citizen participation, under which citizens directly submit proposals to municipal councils regarding specific measures or public policies. For this type of initiative, a qualified majority of voters (at least 10 per cent in municipalities exceeding 20,000 people) are entitled to submit specific proposals to the local government, which must be subsequently voted in the municipal assembly. Due to its legal complexity and demanding requisites, this form of bottom-up participation has been barely used so far.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Arnstein S, 'A Ladder of Citizen Participation' (1969) 35 *Journal of the American Planning Association* 216

Fernández Martínez JL, 'Instituciones de democracia participativa a nivel local: características e impacto de las propuestas participativas sobre políticas públicas' (2016) 8 *Anuario de Derecho Municipal* 144

Velasco Caballero F and Navarro Gómez C, 'The New Urban Agenda and Local Citizen Participation: The Spanish Example' in Nestor Davidson and Greeta Tewari (eds), *Law and the New Urban Agenda* (Routledge 2020)

Gunther R, Gibert JRM, Montero JR, Botella J and Corral JB, *Democracy in Modern Spain* (Yale University Press 2004)

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This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

